

The effectiveness of H9N2 vaccination in commercial broilers flocks under natural field infection.

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Abstract: For decades low pathogenic avian influenza virus (LPAIV) subtype H9N2 was endemic in many Middle Eastern countries including Egypt. The majority of losses associated with the H9N2 virus come from a complicated and mixed infection in commercial broilers specially E-Coli infection. Furthermore, the role of H9N2 vaccination to minimize these losses wasn't evaluated before. In this work, 688,065 Arbor acres broiler chickens from the same breeders' company were distributed equally in four stations, where Two pens were vaccinated against LPAIV of the subtype H9N2 virus and the other two pens served as a non-vaccinated control group, all placed under the same station and management conditions. The flocks exposed to infection around 21 day of live and the results confirmed by PCR, results revealed higher mortality rates in non-vaccinated mixed infected groups with E.Coli and LPAIV of subtype H9N2. In conclusion, using the LPAIV H9N2 vaccine can minimize the loss risk in case of co-infection of E-coli and AIV-H9N2 virus.

Keywords: Avian influenza; Escherichia coli; Broiler

Introduction

LPAIV-H9N2 virus is an endemic disease in many Middle Eastern countries including Egypt, Iran, Israel, Saudi Arabia, and the United Arab Emirates (Nagy, Mettenleiter et al. 2017). The virus has also been isolated regularly in Iraq, Jordan, Kuwait, Lebanon, and Oman (Brown 2010). The majority of H9N2 viruses found in the Middle East are of the G1 'Western' sub-lineage, with occasional isolation of Y439 lineage viruses, likely originating from wild birds (Peacock, Reddy et al. 2016). Despite being detected by real-time RT-PCR in 2006, the first virus isolation of LPAIH9N2 in Egypt dates from December 2010 (El-Zoghby, Arafa et al. 2012). Serological surveillance is done in February 2009 revealed the presence of antibodies against the LPAI H9N2 subtype in domestic poultry flocks (Afifi, El-Kady et al. 2013). Whenever LPAIV of subtype H9N2 virus prevalence has been investigated in lower- and middle-income countries, either by surveys or by passive sampling, the virus is present at extremely high rates, particularly in live bird

markets (LBMs). LBMs are a major component of the disease transmission pathway as well as the spreading of zoonotic infection (Wan, Dong et al. 2011). In countries where (LBMs) are found as Vietnam, China, Bangladesh, and Pakistan prevalence of the virus exceeded 3.5% up to 10% in chickens in LBMs (Guan, Shortridge et al. 2000, Chen, Lin et al. 2016, Thuy, Peacock et al. 2016). In Egypt where (LBMs) are widely found and are considered to be the main market for consumers, the prevalence of LPAIV-H9N2 is about 10% at LBMs in Egypt. For all previously mentioned countries, a degree of hyper-endemicity which is not seen for other influenza virus subtypes is found, potentially due to the LPAIV phenotype of the virus allowing repeated re-infections of the same birds and flocks and as well in the layers and breeders (which have longer life span than broilers). Silent spreading also occurs between farms and backyards birds (Peacock, Reddy et al. 2016).

Co-infections of LPAIV-H9N2 with other respiratory pathogens, as infectious bronchitis virus (IBV), *Mycoplasma gallisepticum*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*,

Ornithobacterium rhinotracheale can exacerbate H9N2 infection resulting in high morbidity and mortality rates (Hassan, El-Kady et al. 2019). With the objective of better control of LPAIV of subtype, H9N2 in broiler chickens in Egypt this study aims to evaluate the benefit of vaccination of LPAIV of subtype H9N2 in broiler chickens as well as evaluation of the effect of avian pathogenic E.Coli (APEC) in coinfections with LPAIV of subtype H9N2 in broiler flocks.

Materials and Methods

Ethical approval

Animal studies were approved by the Animal Welfare and Research Ethics Committee of Banha University and all procedures were conducted strictly following the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals. Every effort was made to minimize animal suffering.

Birds and vaccines

Four broiler farms located in Giza and Qualubia governorates, farms A, B, C, and D. Farms A and B are placed of day-old chicks produced from the same Arbor Acres broiler breeder flock in November 2020. Farms C and D are placed of day-old chicks produced from the same Arbor Acres broiler breeder flock in December 2020. All birds in farms A, B, C, and D got vaccines for IBD (Univax BD, MSD company on day one of life then Bursin plus, Zoetis company at day 13 of life), MEFLUVAC H5+ND combined vaccine (MEVAC Company, Egypt), and IB vaccine (Polimun IB H120, Biotest lab company at day-one of life, Nobilis IB Ma5, MSD company at day 10 of life) as they routinely vaccinated in commercial broilers in Egypt. Farms A and C got vaccinated MEFLUVAC H5+H9+ND combined vaccine (MEVAC Company, Egypt). All vaccines were used as the manufacturer's recommendations and procedures of application. Birds kept under field condition undergo regular monitoring by RT-PCR for common pathogen including AIV-H5, AIV-H9, NDV, IBV, IBD, Avian Astrovirus, Avian Nephritis virus using primers set owned by CPC-lab (Unpublished data) and Agepath mastrix mix kit (thermofisher, USA) and used according to manufacturer instructions.

Experiment Design

Field monitored groups:

A total of 688,065 broiler chickens (Arbor Acres) produced from vaccinated broiler breeder flock with H9N2 vaccine and showing maternally derived antibodies for H9N2 virus (MDA) were placed in 4 Farms, Farm A with 117,170 birds G-1-3 placed at November 2020 in Giza governorate and vaccinated with MEFLUVAC H5+H9+ND combined vaccine (MEVAC Company, Egypt) at 10th days of age. Farm B with 119,175 birds G-4-6 placed in November 2020 in Giza governorate and vaccinated with MEFLUVACH5+ND combined vaccine (MEVAC Company, Egypt) at 10th days of age. Farm C with 200,730 birds placed in December 2020 in Qualubia governorate and vaccinated with MEFLUVACH5+H9+ND combined vaccine (MEVAC Company, Egypt) at 10th days of age. Farm D with 250,990 birds placed in December 2020 in Qualubia governorate and vaccinated with MEFLUVACH5+ND combined vaccine (MEVAC Company, Egypt) at 10th days of age. Birds in farms A, B, C, and D were produced from the same broiler breeder flock and the same hatchery and kept under commercial field conditions with proper biosecurity measures and took the same ratio and management standards. Farms A and B are located in the same area in Giza governorate and chicks are placed on the same day, while farms C and D are located in the same area in Qualubia governorate, and chicks are placed on the same day. All vaccines were used as per manufacturer recommendations.

Hemagglutination inhibition test (HI)

HI test was used to monitor humoral immune response for each vaccine, using avian influenza H9N2, H5N1(Clade 2.2.1.1), H5N1 (Clade 2.2.1.2), H5N8, and ND antigens representing the circulating viruses in Egypt. For avian influenza viruses: chicken sera were examined for HA-specific antibodies by HI test according to the OIE manual (OIE 2015). Serial two-fold serum dilutions in PBS were subsequently mixed with equal volumes (25 µl) of the virus-containing 4 hemagglutinating units (HAU), then 25 µl of washed chicken red blood cells were added. After incubation for 40 min at room

temperature, HI titers were determined as reciprocals of the highest serum dilutions in which inhibition of hemagglutination was observed. For Newcastle disease virus: chicken sera were examined for HA-specific antibodies by HI test according to the OIE manual (OIE 2012). Serial two-fold serum dilutions in PBS were subsequently mixed with equal volumes (25 μ l) of the virus-containing 4 hemagglutinating units (HAU), then 25 μ l of washed chicken red blood cells were added. After incubation for 40 min at room temperature, HI titers were determined as reciprocals of the highest serum dilutions in which inhibition of hemagglutination was observed.

Statistical analysis

Whenever necessary, data were analyzed by the student's t-test or by ANOVA followed by the application of Duncan's new multiple range test to determine the significance of differences between individual treatments and corresponding control (Steel and Torrie 1960).

Results

Field groups performance parameters

Field groups final cumulative performance parameters

Field performance parameters for different farms were monitored on daily basis and results are shown in Table 1. *The cumulative mortalities showed 4.00%, 5.17%, 6.79%, and 8.59% in groups D, C, B, and A respectively. Feed conversion rate FCR values showed 1.42, 1.49, 1.53, and 1.67 in groups D, C, B, and A respectively. European production efficiency factor EPEF values showed 376, 339, 317, and 263 in groups D, C, B, and A respectively.*

Weekly average weight gain

Average weekly weight gain for different farms was recorded and showed 173.6, 189, 213.9, and 211.9 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 1st week of life, and 470.4, 454.3, 537.1, and 521.6 grams in groups D, C, B, and A

respectively for 2nd week of life, and 908.4, 903, 1015, and 998.8 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 3rd week of life, and 1518.1, 1510.5, 1529.9, and 1445 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 4th week of life as shown in Figure 1.

Daily mortality percentage

Daily mortality percentage for different farms was recorded; Farm A showed increased daily mortality rate from 28th of life, Farm B showed increased daily mortality rate from 29th day of life, farm C showed increased daily mortality rate from 33rd day of life, while farm D showed stability in daily mortality rate till last day of life (33rd day of life) as shown in Figure 2.

Pathogens detections in field groups

Different pathogens were detected by qRT-PCR in different field groups and were recorded by age of detection; AIV was detected in all farms., H9N2 was detected in farms A, and B., IB was detected in farms A, B, and D., Infectious bursal disease IBD was detected in farm A., ND was detected in farms A, B, and D., Astrovirus was detected in farms A, and B., Avian nephritis virus was detected in farm A as shown in Table 2.

Serology monitoring in field groups

AIV H9N2 titers monitoring in field groups

Random serum samples were collected from different farms at 4, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days of life for monitoring antibody titers for AIV H9N2 as shown in Table 3., Figure 3.

Other diseases titers monitoring in field groups

Random serum samples were collected from different farms at 4, 7, 14, 21, and 28 days of life for monitoring antibody titers for ND using Lasota, and ND Genotype VII antigens as shown in Table 4. And for AIV H5 using AIV (H5N1 clade 2.2.1.1), AIV (H5N1 clade 2.2.1.2), and AIV (H5N8 clade 2.3.4.4) antigens as shown in Table-5.

Table 1. Field performance parameters for different farms

Farm	Head Placed	Cumulative mortality %	Culls %	AWS	FCR	EPEF	AHG	ADGW	TMC
Farm A	117,170	8.59	4.90	1.509	1.67	263	31.32	48.16	2.181
Farm B	119,175	6.79	2.50	1.582	1.53	317	30.31	52.18	2.363
Farm C	200,730	5.17	0.00	1.708	1.49	339	32.12	53.16	2.766
Farm D	250,990	4.00	1.41	1.651	1.42	376	29.90	55.22	2.403

KG= Kilogram; FCR= Feed conversion rate; EPEF= European production efficiency factor; EGP= Egyptian pound. AHG: Average Harvest Age (Day); ADGW: Average Daily Weight Gain (Gram); AWS: Average Weight Sold (KG); TMC: Total Medication Cost per KG (EGP)

Figure 1: Weekly average weight gain for different farms

Figure 2: Daily mortality percentage for different farms

Table 2. Pathogens detections in field groups

Farm	AIV General	H9N2	IB	IBD	ND	Astro	ANV
Age of detection (Days)							
Farm A	2,21,25,31	27,31	2,4,18,25	25	18,27,31	2	25
Farm B	21,31	30	19		30	3	
Farm C	8						
Farm D	4		14		4		

ANV= Avian nephritis virus

Table 3. AIV H9N2 HI test results for different field groups

GMT Log ₂ HI titre (n=15)					
	Age (Days)	Farm A	Farm B	Farm C	Farm D
AIV (H9N2)	4	7.3±0.41	8.2±0.33	7.7±0.20	7.4±0.27
	7	6.1±0.27	7.8±0.33	6.4±0.29	6.2±0.40
	14	3.8±0.19	4.9±0.20	4.8±0.39	3.7±0.20
	21	4.3±0.12	2.5±0.13	3.1±0.27	3.6±0.26
	28	3.8±0.29	2.3±0.15	3.1±0.29	1.9±0.20

Figure 3: AIV H9N2 HI test results graph with error bars for different field groups

Table 4. ND HI test results for different field groups

GMT Log ₂ HI titre (n=15)					
Antigen	Age (Days)	Farm A	Farm B	Farm C	Farm D
ND (Lasota)	4	5.6±0.16	6.2±0.22	6.8±0.17	7.3±0.27
	7	4.6±0.15	4.8±0.29	5.2±0.21	5.4±0.51
	14	4.5±0.17	4.2±0.20	4.1±0.26	4.6±0.38
	21	4.3±0.29	5.2±0.38	4.4±0.40	4.2±0.18
	28	3±0.26	3.6±0.37	4±0.21	4±0.17
ND (Genotype VII)	4	6.1±0.27	8.2±0.40	7.1±0.27	7.4±0.31

7	4.3±0.15	5.1±0.27	5±0.18	5.4±0.49
14	3.6±0.24	3.3±0.21	3.8±0.38	3.7±0.33
21	3.2±0.20	3.2±0.27	3.2±0.28	3.2±0.28
28	4.4±0.34	5.1±0.28	4.2±0.20	4.1±0.55

Table 5. AIV H5 HI test results for different field groups

Antigen	Age (Days)	GMT Log2 HI titre (n=15)			
		Farm A	Farm B	Farm C	Farm D
AIV (H5N1) (2.2.1.1)	4	6.3±0.28	5.9±0.33	6.8±0.24	7.1±0.27
	7	4.9±0.29	3±0.30	6.5±0.22	6.2±0.28
	14	3.2±0.30	3.4±0.34	4.4±0.34	4.5±0.40
	21	4±0.37	4.1±0.31	4.1±0.43	4.3±0.56
	28	3.7±0.45	3.3±0.47	3.7±0.54	3.8±0.42
AIV (H5N1) (2.2.1.2)	4	5.5±0.26	5.6±0.20	5.5±0.26	6.3±0.47
	7	4.2±0.22	5.2±0.25	6.6±0.27	5.9±0.34
	14	3.4±0.24	3.7±0.21	4.1±0.48	4.3±0.54
	21	3.7±0.21	3.1±0.38	3.7±0.21	3.2±0.34
	28	4.1±0.48	4.2±0.25	4.2±0.36	4±0.30
AIV (H5N8)	4	6.1±0.29	6.2±0.49	5.8±0.17	5.4±0.33
	7	3.7±0.21	4.5±0.34	4.9±0.27	4.5±0.31
	14	2.8±0.25	3.1±0.34	3.4±0.33	3.1±0.25
	21	3.6±0.24	3.4±0.42	3.1±0.31	3.4±0.49
	28	3.9±0.30	4.1±0.47	4±0.21	3.9±0.35

Discussion

Regarding the cumulative mortalities in the different groups, birds kept in Qualubia showed significantly lower mortalities in comparison to the birds kept in Saff Giza, as the latter has a high exposure level of poultry pathogens especially avian influenza, NDV, and IB while in Qualubia the epidemiological level showed lower viral load. Birds in group-C (vaccinated in Qualubia) showed higher mortalities in comparison to birds in group-D (non-vaccinated in Qualubia) and thus disagree with previous reports by Talat et al (2020) who mentioned that the AIV-H9N2 vaccine can be associated with lower mortalities (Talat, Abouelmaatti et al. 2020), although if we combined the mortalities percentages with culls percentage in those group, the birds in group-C (vaccinated showed lowered mortalities and culls % in comparison to Bird in group-D (Non-

vaccinated); thus may explain the difference in the obtained results from Talat et al (2020), which may be associated to increase the level of culls in group-D in comparison to group-C (1.41 and 0%, respectively). Birds in Group-C (vaccinated) showed a higher average selling weight (1,708 kg) in comparison to birds in group-D (1.651KG), although both birds groups were exposed to early infection by Avian influenza H9N2 virus. Also, increased mortalities in D-farm may be associated with prolonged selling times as its average selling age is 32.12 vs 29.9 days in farm-C and the selling applied toward live bird market, and it is known that prolonged selling time is associated with increased mortalities due to partially broken to the biosecurity standers due to frequent truck entering to farm to carry chicks (Elhady, Ali et al. 2018, Kandeil, Hicks et al. 2019).

Regarding the average weekly weight gain, the birds kept in Giza showed a significantly lower

rate in comparison to the birds kept in Qualiobia station and thus may be associated with better farm equipment and better epidemiological situation in Qualubia in comparison to the El-Saff-Giza area (Hassan, Shany et al. 2016, Hassan, El-Kady et al. 2021).

birds in farm-A showed a significant drop in weekly weight gain and thus may be associated with exposure to IBD which affect the immune system and Avian Nephritis virus (ANV) which affect the kidney functions and chicken metabolism, thus supported by previous reports by Narita et al (1991) who reported that, co-infection of IBD with ANV associated with severe immunosuppression (Narita, Umiji et al. 1991).

Average weekly weight gain for different farms was recorded and showed 173.6, 189, 213.9, and 211.9 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 1st week of life, and 470.4, 454.3, 537.1, and 521.6 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 2nd week of life, and 908.4, 903, 1015, and 998.8 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 3rd week of life, and 1518.1, 1510.5, 1529.9, and 1445 grams in groups D, C, B, and A respectively for 4th week of life

The birds in all groups either vaccinated with H5H9ND or H5ND vaccine showed similar seroconversion for H5 and ND and only birds in groups A and C (vaccinated groups) showed seroconversion for AIV-H9N2 on day 28 of life while birds in group A and D (non-vaccinated group) did not show a detectable level of seroconversion and thus confirmed that the combination of three different pathogens in one inactivated vaccine as trivalent (H5H9ND as applied in, MEFLUVAC-H5H9ND) provide immune response similar to the bivalent vaccine (H5ND) and birds vaccinated with vaccine contain H9 at day 9 of life developed seroconversion for AIV-H9N2 at 28 days of life which agreed with previous reports (Talat, Abouelmaatti et al. 2020).

Conclusions

The coinfection of AIV-H9N2 may be the actual cause for the exaggerated losses associated with H9N2 infections in commercial broilers in

endemic countries. The application of the AIV-H9N2 inactivated vaccine strategy in commercial broilers may add value for controlling the infection and complications associated with it as E-coli and other common viral infections as Infectious bronchitis virus especially in the 4th-5th weeks of birdlife.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest, The funders had no role in the design of the study; in the collection, analyses, or interpretation of data; in the writing of the manuscript, or in the decision to publish the results.

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